

CONCEPTUAL STUDY OF KANDUGNA MAHAKASHAYA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DADRU KUSHTA (TINEA)**¹Das B., ²Choudhury D.N., ³Hussain M. M.**¹Associate Professor, ²Assistant Professor, ³PG Scholar.¹Dept. of Clinical Toxicology, Govt. Ayurvedic College, Guwahati.^{2,3}Dept. of Samhita Siddhanta, Govt. Ayurvedic College, Guwahati.

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda the ancient system of medicine plays a vital role in management of disease and maintain a positive health. In other word we can say that health is the ultimate goal of Ayurveda. All the skin diseases are described under the term of Kushtha kandu or itching is a symptoms of various types of skin disease. In kandu, kapha is the predominant dosha followed by vata and pitta. Dadru, Charmadal, Pama etc. are few dermatological diseases where kandu is the main symptom. Dadru kushta is a skin disease which is associated with severe itching leading to hamper in day to day activities of the sufferer. Charaka was described Kandugna Mahakashaya in the 4th chapter of Sutrasthana. Chandana, Nalada, Kritmala, Naklamala, Nimba, Kulaka, Sarsapa, Madluka, Daruharidra and Musta are 10 medicinal plants under the Kandugna Mahakashaya. Details

literary review of the Kandugna Mahakashaya reveals that it plays a vital role in the management of Dadru Kushta where kandu or severe itching is a cardinal manifestation.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Kandu, Pruritus, Kushta, Dadru, Kandugna Mahakashaya.**INTRODUCTION**

Kandu is a symptom manifested due to dermatological disorder and other underlying systemic disease. It an unpleasant experience of itching on the skin which provokes the desire to scratch. It can be localised or spread throughout the parts of the body. It is not mentioned

as separate entity in Ayurveda. It is either a purvaroop (primordial symptom) or roopa (symptom) or upadrava (complications) or asadya lakshana (incurable symptom) of one or other systematic disease. Although Kapha is the predominant dosha involved in kandu (Pruritus) but there is also association of Vata and Pitta dosha.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM

To find out the role of Kandugna Mahakashaya in the management of Dadru Kushta.

OBJECTIVE

- To study the kandughna mahakashaya.
- To study botanical name, family of kandughna mahakashaya.
- To study the rasa panchaka of the kandughna mahakashaya.
- To study the effect of kandughna mahakashaya in the management of kandu of Dadru kushta.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

- i. Authentic classical Ayurvedic books.
- ii. Authentic book of modern pharmacognosy & pharmacology.
- iii. Internal & encyclopedia.

Method: Kandugna

- i. Classical Ayurvedic books will be studied to know the Mahakashaya along with Rasa panchaka.
- ii. Modern book on Pharmacognosy & pharmacology will be studied for proper identification & their action.
- iii. Relevant datas will be collected from internal & encyclopedia.

LITERARY REVIEW

- i. There are 10 medicinal plants under Kandughna Mahakashya.
- ii. Identification is an integral part of a scientific study.
- iii. Detailed of the medicinal plants of Kandughna Mahakashaya along with their botanical and family name in table no.1

Table No.1.

Sl No	Sanskrit name	Botanical name	Family
1	Chandana	<i>Santalum album</i>	Santalaceae
2	Nalada	<i>Nardostchys</i>	Valerianaceae
3	Kritamala	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Caesalpinaceae
4	Naktamala	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Papilionaceae
5	Nimba	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Meliaceae
6	Kutaja	<i>Holarrhena antidysenterica</i>	Apocynaceae
7	Sarshapa	<i>Brassica juncea</i>	Brassicaceae
8	Madhuka	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Papilionacea
9	Daru haridra	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	Berberidaceae
10	Musta	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	Cyperaceae

In Ayurveda Rasa panchak i.e. rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipaka & Karma are the main source through which we can estimate the mode of action of a medicine or a group of medicine. Study of rasa panchak i.e. very important to know the efficacy of a medicinal plant. Rasa panchak of Kandugna Mahakashya are summarized in table no. 2.

Table No. 2.

No.	Name of the medicinal plants	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Karma
1	Chandana	Tikta, Madhura	Ruksha, Laghu	Sheeta	Madhura	Pittashamana, Dahashamana, Kandughna
2	Nalada	Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Snigdha	Sheeta	Katu	Tridosahara, Manashamaka
3	Kritamala	Madhura, Tikta	Guru, Snigdha	Sheeta	Madhura	Pittashamana, Kandughna
4	Naktamala	Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Tikshna	Ushna	Katu	Kandughna, Krimighna
5	Nimba	Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Ruksha	Sheeta	Katu	Kandughna, Pittashamana
6	Kutaja	Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Ruksha	Sheeta	Katu	Kandughna, Rakta-shodhaka
7	Sarshapa	Katu, Tikshna	Tikshna, Snigdha	Ushna	Katu	Kaphahara, Kandughna
8	Madhuka	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha	Sheeta	Madhura	Pittashamana, Kandughna
9	Daru haridra	Tikta, Kashaya	Ruksha, Laghu	Ushna	Katu	Raktashodhaka, Kandughna
10	Musta	Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Ruksha	Sheeta	Katu	Pittashamana, Kandughna

Modern Pharmacology guide us to know the action of a medicine with regard to systemic and local action. Anti-pruritic action, anti-stress, Anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory and anti-bacterial are few modern pharmacological properties of the medicinal plants under

Kandughana Mahakashaya. All the modern pharmacological properties of Kandughana Mahakashaya are tabulated in table no.3.

Table No. 3.

No.	Drug	Pharmacological Properties
1	Chandana	Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory
2	Nalada	Calms CNS-mediated itching
3	Kranthamala	anti-inflammatory
4	Naktamala	antimicrobial & antiparasitic
5	Nimba	Antihistamine-like effect, antimicrobial
6	Kutaja	Anti- parasites, anti-inflammatory
7	Sarshapa	Antimicrobial
8	Madhuka	anti-inflammatory, reduces allergic itching
9	Daruharidra	Anti-bacterial, Anti-fungal
10	Musta	anti-inflammatory,

DISCUSSION

In Ayurveda, the term Kustha holds a very important role. The disease where there is disfigurement is termed as Kustha. There are total 18 types of kustha as per Ayurveda classics viz Mahakustha and kshudra kustha. The number of Mahakustha is 7 where there are 11 no. of kshudra kustha. Considering the description of kustha it is very relevant to various dermatological disorders. Vata, pitta, kapha are the 3 vital factors responsible for both health and diseases. In the pathogenesis of kustha roga all the three doshas are vitiated. These vitiated tri dosha leading to vitiation of twak, rakta, mamsa and ambu. So, these seven factors vata, pitta, kapha, twak, rakta, mamsa and ambu are main reason for manifestation of kustha. In Ayurveda it is mentioned that wholesome diet and regimen, improper panchakarma as well as excessive fear, grief and past sinful acts are the major contributing factors for manifestation of kustha. Dadru Kushta is an Ayurvedic term for a common, contagious skin condition, clinically similar to modern Tinea infection (Ringworm), characterized by red, itchy, circular patches (Mandalas) with eruptions (Pidakas) and inflammation (Raga), involving aggravated Kapha and Pitta Doshas.

In Ayurveda, "kandu" refers to itching or pruritus, an unpleasant sensation on the skin that provokes the desire to scratch. Tinea is a common, contagious fungal skin infection, also known as ringworm, that affects skin, hair, and nails, causing itchy, red, scaly patches, often ring-shaped. Analysis of Rasa of Kandughana Mahakashaya suggest that it is having the predominancy of Tikta rasa (40 %) followed by tikta - madhura (20 %), tikta - Kashaya (10 %), Madhura (10 %), Tikta katu (10 %), Tikta-katu-kashya (10 %) the predominant rasa of

this mahakashaya is Tikta & madhura are capable of pacifying kapha dosha which is the main reason of kandu the cardinal symptoms of dadru. Again there is tikta-kasa-rasa (10 %), which are key factors for pacification of kapha dosha i.e. kandu. Due to tikta, madhura and Kashaya rasa these plants are capable of subsiding kapha dosha. In Kandughana Mahakashaya laghu & ruksha, guna is predominat i.e. (50%). Virya of Kandughana Mahakashaya is sheeta (70%) and vipaka is Madhura (80%). These drugs have pitta-kapha as dominant dosha karma i.e. (50%) so analyzing the rasa panchaka we can say that Kandughana Mahakashaya will be subsiding kandu due to its nature and properties.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion we can say that, the medicinal plants of Kandughana Mahakashaya plays an important role in the management of Kandu which is the cardinal symptoms of Dadru Kushtha i.e. Tinea.

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